

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.

- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- When possible, round off numbers to one or two decimal points. For example, 5.2 t/ha, *not* 5.232.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-spaced. ~~WY~~

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Variability in daily grain production per hectare in rice

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In northern India the rice-growing season is limited to from mid-May to the end of October. Therefore, it is essential to develop varieties that take no more than

100 days to mature in the field to permit the timely sowing of the primary rabi crop, wheat, in November. The yield potential of such varieties should be equal to or better than that of the present commercially grown high yielding varieties.

The present concept in rice breeding is to develop a genotype that makes the best use of available nutrients and solar

Table 1. Duration and daily grain production per hectare of 218 rice varieties during 1976 kharif (wet season), Kapurthala, India.

Grain production/ha (kg)	Varieties (no.) of different growth duration						Total
	80-90 days	91-100 days	101-110 days	111-120 days	121-130 days	131-140 days	
25 - 30	—	—	—	—	—	2	2
30 - 35	—	—	—	—	—	2	2
35 - 40	—	—	—	3	3	4	10
40 - 45	—	—	3	9	12	1	25
45 - 50	—	1	6	21	7	1	36
50 - 55	—	2	7	26	15	—	50
55 - 60	—	—	6	24	14	—	44
60 - 65	—	2	7	13	12	—	34
65 - 70	—	—	3	4	1	—	8
70 - 75	—	—	2	—	—	—	3
75 - 80	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
80 - 85	—	1	—	—	—	—	3
85 - 90	—	1	—	—	—	—	1
	2	7	34	100	65	10	218

Table 2. Daily grain production per hectare of different groups of varieties. Kapurthala, India.

Group	Variety	Field duration (days)	Grain/day per ha (kg)
	<i>Long duration, low yielding</i>		
I	1728	138	28.47
	Basmati 370	131	28.40
	<i>Short duration, high yielding</i>		
II	PR 103	92	86.74
	IR1561-228-3-3	91	82.42
	MTU 6368-89	89	82.37
	RP 379-34-8 1-1 3	90	81.33
	<i>Recommended high yielding</i>		
III	Jaya	117	66.10
	PR 106	119	65.00
	Palman 579	110	53.09

PR 103 yielded 86.7 kg/ha daily in trials at Kapurthala, Punjab, India.

energy in the shortest rice-growing period to give maximum yield per unit of area and per unit of time at a low cost. To identify such efficient type, 218 newly developed, short-statured cultures from various crosses were grown in a replicated yield trial at the Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala. Data on duration in the field and on daily grain

production per hectare were recorded.

Daily grain production per hectare varied widely. Varieties with a growth duration of 80 to 140 days produced 25 kg to 90 kg/day per ha (Table 1). The varieties that performed well are compared with the present high yielding varieties of the Punjab in Table 2.

The varieties in group II of Table 2

show promise as replacements for almost all high yielding varieties of the Punjab; they may also help to prolong the transplanting period. They would also vacate the fields from 10 to 20 days earlier than the presently grown varieties and thus allow farmers to prepare the fields for timely sowing of wheat. The higher daily grain production per hectare of those varieties seems to represent a high physiological capacity to mobilize photosynthates and to translocate these to organs having economic value. A detailed study of the morphophysiological traits of these groups can provide better selection criteria for genetic gain in paddy yield improvement. A conspicuous morphological character of PR 103, which gave the highest daily grain yield of 86.7 kg/day per ha, seems to be its very long (60–80 cm) and upright flag leaf (see photo) that intercepts maximum sunlight during the grain-filling phase in the field. Hybridization programs may use such varieties widely to transfer their desirable traits to other varieties. **W**

Co 40 or Rajarajan — a new high yielding, long-duration monsoon rice

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The monsoon season in the Coromandal coastal belt and Cauvery basin of Tamil Nadu extends from August to December. The monsoon is characterized by factors not normally favorable for increased rice yields — cool temperature (from 25.1°C to 29.7°C), short duration of sunlight (from 5.5 to 8.3 hours/day), monsoon cloudiness, and high rain intensity (from 927 to 1,144 mm in 50–53 rainy days). Despite these unfavorable conditions, 60 to 70% of the rice area in India, particularly in Tamil Nadu (1.62 to 1.69 million ha), is grown to monsoon rice.

In spite of the development of several high yielding varieties, the specific varietal needs for the large monsoonal rice area, including high yield potential

and long growth duration, have not been met. Neither national nor international rice breeding organizations have devoted much effort to the development of rice varieties with growth duration of longer than 140 to 145 days. Varieties with a long vegetative phase and a maturation period of 160 days or more would commence flowering at the end of the monsoon. Panicle emergence would then coincide with bright, dry, cool weather and slowly increasing temperature during the postmonsoon period. Inherently photoperiod-sensitive varieties grown now are tall indicas that yield low, mainly because of poor nitrogen utilization and

susceptibility to lodging and blast *Pyricularia oryzae*. The latest tall indica variety made available for monsoon cultivation is Co 25, from the cross Co 4/ADT-10. Co 25 is resistant to *Pyricularia*, is photoperiod-sensitive, and has a growth duration of 165 to 180 days. But it gives low yields of 3 to 3.5 t/ha (see table), because it lodges even at the early growth stage.

To achieve those objectives, IR8 and Co 25 were crossed in 1969 at the Paddy Breeding Station, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore. A number of derivatives were selected and tested for yield in the

Mean yield of Co 40 Rajarajan rice in the monsoon season (Aug. to Jan.) in Pondicherry and Tamil Nadu regions, India.

Trials	Yield (t/ha)				Mean
	1974	1975	1976	1977	
Rice research station	7.5	6.8	6.7	6.6	6.9
Adaptive trials in farmers' fields	—	5.6	6.1	6.0	5.9
Demonstration in farmers' fields	—	—	6.4	6.6	6.5
Mean	7.5	6.2	6.5	6.5	6.1
Local check (Co 25)	3.7	2.6	4.1	3.7	3.5